

IJTIMOY HAMKORLIK ASOSIDA TALABALARNING PEDAGOGIK MALAKALARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH USULLARI.

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Annotatsiya: Hamkorlikda o'qitish texnologiyasi har bir talabaning bilim olishdagi muvafaqqiyati guruh muvafaqqiyatiga olib kelishini anglashini, mustaqil va sidqidildan aqliy mehnat qilishga, bilim olishga, o'quv topshiriqlarini to'liq va sifatli bajarishga o'quv materialini puxta o'zlashtirishga, o'rtoqlariga hamkor bo'lib, o'zaro fikr almashishga zamin tayyorlashi haqida ma'lumot berilib o'tildi. Maqolada talabalarda ijtimoiy faollik ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishda motivlashtirish va motivatsiyaning o'rni hamda ularni amaliyotga tatbiq etishning ahamiyati ilmiy asoslangan holda tadqiq etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Motivatsiya, ijtimoiy faollik, shaxs tushunchasi, insonparvarlik, bilim-tarbiya jarayonlari, ijtimoiy faoliyat, o'qish, o'rganish, pedagogik jarayonlar, metod, yondashuv, takomillashtirish.

Annotation: Cooperative teaching technology allows each student to understand that the success of learning leads to the success of the group, to independently and diligently work intellectually, to acquire knowledge, to complete educational tasks fully and qualitatively, to master the educational material thoroughly, to study information was given on how to become a partner and prepare the ground for mutual exchange of ideas. In the article, the role of motivation and motivation in the formation of social activity skills in students, as well as the importance of their practical application, is researched on a scientific basis.

Key words: Motivation, social activity, concept of personality, humanitarianism, educational processes, social activity, reading, learning,

pedagogical processes, method, approach, improvement. Sovershenstvovanie pedagogicheskoy podgotovki studentov na osnove sotsialnogo sotrudnichestva.

Аннотация: Технология кооперативного обучения позволяет каждому студенту понять, что успех обучения ведет к успеху группы, самостоятельно и усердно работать интеллектуально, приобретать знания, полно и качественно выполнять учебные задания, основательно усваивать учебный материал, В ходе исследования была дана информация о том, как стать партнером и подготовить почву для взаимного обмена идеями. В статье на научной основе исследуется роль мотивации и мотивации в формировании навыков социальной деятельности у студентов, а также важность их практического применения.

Ключевые слова: Мотивация, социальная активность, концепция личности, гуманизм, образовательные процессы, социальная активность, чтение, обучение, педагогические процессы, метод, подход, совершенствование.

Introduction: The idea of cooperative education was developed by R. Slavin, professor of J. Hopkins University in America, R. Johnson, professor of Minnesota University, D. Johnson, professor of California University - SH. Sharon. Collaborative teaching developed by American scientists, mainly for the formation of knowledge, skills and competencies in students, collaborative teaching recommended by Israeli and European scientists, as mentioned above, more students are involved in the design of learning material processing activities. development, educational debate and discussions. These ideas complement each other, for example, doactively enrich and require each other. The idea of cooperative teaching appeared in didactics in the 1970s. The technology of cooperative education is widely used in educational institutions of Great Britain, Canada, Germany, Australia, the Netherlands, Japan, and Israel. The main idea of cooperative education is not only to complete educational tasks together, but also

to study and learn cooperatively. Collaborative teaching is to teach every student to daily intensive mental work, to think creatively and independently, to educate individual consciousness and independence, to create and develop a sense of personal worth in each student, to develop their own strength and abilities. It envisages the strengthening of confidence, the formation of a sense of responsibility in acquiring knowledge. The technology of cooperative education allows students to work independently and diligently mentally, acquire knowledge, complete educational tasks in full and quality, thoroughly master the educational material, cooperate with their peers, realizing that the success of each student in learning leads to the success of the group. and prepares the ground for exchange of ideas. In cooperative learning technology, there are several methods of organizing cooperative learning of students:

Literature analysis: Teaching in teams (R. Slavin) in which students are divided into two teams of equal number. Both teams perform the same task. The members of the team perform the educational tasks in cooperation, and each student focuses on mastering the knowledge, skills and abilities provided by the subject. R. Slavin, one of the authors of cooperative learning technology, said that it is not enough to instruct students to complete tasks cooperatively. It is necessary for students to work together in the literal sense, to rejoice at the success of each student, to form a feeling of sincere help to each other, and to create a comfortable social and psychological environment. In this technology, in order to determine the quality of students' knowledge acquisition, they are compared not with each other, but with the previous results of each student. Only then, students, realizing that the result achieved during the lesson will benefit the team, feel responsible and strive to learn more, acquire knowledge, skills and abilities.

2. Collaborative teaching in small groups (R. Slavin, 1986). In this approach, small groups consist of four students. The teacher first explains the topic, and then students' independent work is organized. The educational assignments given to the

students are divided into four parts, and each student performs a certain part of the assignment. At the end of the task, each student thinks about the part he has completed, and then the group members make a general conclusion about the task. The student listens to the information of each small group and evaluates the knowledge with the help of test questions. Educational activities of students in small groups can be organized in the form of games, competitions, and individually. In research on the cooperative activity of the teacher and the student, the main attention is focused on the study of the development of interaction, the process of group organization of teaching is described. Psychologist A.V. Petrovsky studied that the interpersonal relations in the team originate from the activity and emphasized that organizing the cooperation of the teacher with the students in the educational process is not only a means of satisfying their need for communication, but also a means of mastering the educational material.

Forms of teacher-student cooperation are an important factor of mutual cooperation and the basis determining the nature of student interaction. Collaborative educational activity is a special type of teacher-student relationship and joint behavior, which provides the object of mastery, reconstruction of all parts of knowledge activity. The goal of cooperative learning activities is to create a control mechanism of mastery activities and joint actions, attitudes and communication. The product of cooperative activity is the emergence of new ideas put forward by students and goals related to the essence of the activity being mastered, and the desire to manage the individual's position in partnership. The method of cooperative activity should be understood as the system of joint actions of the teacher and the student. Such behavior begins with the teacher's help to the student; The students' activity gradually increases and becomes a practical and intellectual action completely controlled by them; and the relationship between the teacher and the student will have the character of partnership position. In the world, a number of scientific researches are being carried out to improve the

technology of developing the social activity of students of higher education institutions and to develop new pedagogical tools to support their social initiative, to develop the skills of effective organization of socio-cultural and communicative activities. As the most important factors for the development of social activity, the development of moral-aesthetic worldview and political socialization in students is given special recognition. Also, as pedagogical mechanisms of social activity, it is important to develop the spiritual and cultural foundations of moral, professional and communicative preparation of students, their conscious attitude to the ideas of development and their scientific thinking. In our republic, special attention is paid to the improvement of the content of higher education and the processes of personnel training based on advanced foreign experiences, and the development of social competences in students as important directions of spiritual and educational work.

The relationship with the motive is the basis of the direct implementation of mental activity

is manifested through calculated activity.

Analysis and result. There is a lot of information about cooperation in the literature. So, social cooperation is considered as a high form of activity. "The term social cooperation is used to define the social activity of people in a certain system of social relations, as well as to define the ability to carry it out. Being such an ability, social activity exists as a complex, integral virtue. It represents some special feature, but the whole set of features of vital activity. The social activity of students is related to the social activity of the knowledge communities where they study, work, and acquire life experience.

One of the important tasks is to increase and develop creative abilities of future educators, to form the technique of organizing didactic games in preschool children through these abilities. [1] Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarda kreativ qobiliyatlarni oshirish va rivojlantirish, ushbu qobiliyatlar orqali maktabgacha yoshdagi

bolalarda didaktik o'yinlarni tashkil etish texnikasini shakllantirish muhim vazifalardan biridir. [1]

Training of socially active students and competitive personnel is national in our society

It is democratic and national because it is conducted on the basis of the idea of independence

earns. In this regard, it is based on dominance, submission and obedience pedagogy is replaced by humanization of knowledge, creativity, science, cooperation,

the principles of social activity and the priority of friendly relations are followed. A command-free management style is being introduced. In the team, attention is being paid to the human factor, and a spiritual and spiritual environment is being created based on human qualities such as kindness, social protection, honesty, truthfulness and justice. Social activity is a complex process that does not occur in a person all of a sudden. The conducted studies showed that the formation of social cooperation in the personality of a student corresponds to the period when he chooses this profession. The sooner a teacher realizes the responsibility and difficult aspects of his profession, especially for the benefit of the people, the faster the buds of social activity will be formed. This situation can be said in other professions as well. Based on this, it can be said that a student who can stand in a position of aspiration in the process of professional activity is called a socially active student. The "motive" that encourages social activity can serve as a factor that determines the student's personal desires, interests, future dreams, and interest in his profession.

The concept of social cooperation, scientific research in the last 10 years entering more widely and deeply into the content and practice of pedagogical activity

is going The analysis shows that this concept comes from the socio-economic sphere,

is moving to the pedagogical field. From the point of view of cooperation in education, economic and legal issues are first analyzed (the interests of pedagogical staff and their legal protection, the interaction of the employer, the trade union and the community, the implementation of legislation in education based on cooperation, the modernization of international cooperation in education, etc.). [2]

It shows that students' activity in the learning process clarifies their interest in their profession. In this process, groups with a low level of discipline, organization and responsibility can be stopped. On the other hand, the success of student activity development depends on the individual qualities and motivation of each of them. It is difficult to imagine the process of forming social activity without motivation. Of course, the motivational approach is effective in researching this process. The motivational approach has both theoretical and practical importance, and its theoretical importance is seen in the fact that it is focused on the study of the psychological mechanisms and peculiarities of attracting the student to study, providing effective knowledge, and its practical importance is related to theoretical knowledge. based on the formation and development of positive motives in students. Therefore, the motivational approach is an important factor in the development of social activity of students.

Today, the care given to young people by our state, the opportunities created, create great opportunities for them to work on themselves, to constantly research and quickly learn new things, and to acquire knowledge at the level of modern requirements. [3]

Motivating students in the process of forming their social activity skills means the essence, importance and necessity of the concept of social activity, humanitarianism, hard work, selflessness, forming children worthy of their people

and nation, loyalty and faith, volition, freedom and tolerance. , it is important to master concepts such as teaching respect for values such as honesty and to form positive motives that generate interest in learning these concepts, and they serve to form and develop social activity in students.

Conclusions and recommendations: To sum up, education of the young generation in the spirit of social activity is one of the urgent tasks of today. The emergence and understanding of behavior. A complete understanding of the behavior is the effect of the action

understanding and determining the methods and results of this action in advance. Acceptance of motives, which represents the implementation of actions based on internal motives. At this stage, a person analyzes his moral principles and values, makes a decision about the need, inclination and how important it is for him and the need to satisfy them. This is the stage of the implementation of the motive, and in this process, the content of the motives may change depending on the situation. There is a stage of strengthening of the motive, and as a result of this stage, the motive becomes a character symbol. It is a process of activation of behavior, and in this process, a certain feature of the strengthened motive (character) comes to the field, consciously or unconsciously. Therefore, motivation is based on certain needs, and it is appropriate to direct students' activities by means of psychological influence.

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